

PHENET

PHENOTYPING & ENVIROTypING
SOLUTIONS FOR AGROecology

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EXTERNAL STAKEHOLDER SESSION

See the Future of Agroecology Tech in Action

Join us for live demonstrations of the tools, services, and innovations developed across our use cases by the researchers who built them.

DATE
 Thursday, 10 September 2026

TIME
 14:00 – 17:00 CEST

VENUE
 Earth & Life Institute, UCLouvain — Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium

WHAT TO EXPECT

01 Introduction to PHENET
Short pitch on the project and its candidate services ready for deployment

02 Live demonstrations
Developers present their tools, outputs and technologies

03 One-on-one exchange
Private sessions with technology developers to discuss your needs

04 Networking across sectors
Connect with researchers, industry partners, farmers and policymakers

TECHNOLOGIES & TOOLS ON SHOW

● Computer vision for wheat disease detection: G3 smart glasses & smartphone app & MobiLab

● Investigating soil and ecosystem phenomena with controlled environment setups

● Digital soil surveying & mapping with Subterra Green

● IntercropAgent: an AI tool for intercropping meta-analysis from scientific literature

● Phenomobile Demo & deep learning for apple orchard phenology across European environments

● SoilMap: Service for soil health & landscape monitoring

● IoT sensor networks for real-time field monitoring

● Bee colonies as indicators of ecosystem & landscape health

WHO SHOULD ATTEND

Research Infrastructures

Living Labs

AI & EO Tech

Farming & Agroecology

R&D Forestry

Seed & Plant Businesses

Researchers

Extension Services

R&D Fruit Farming

Policy Makers

REGISTRATION OPEN

Attendance by registration & invitation

Spaces are limited - secure yours early

[Register Now](#) →

